

NDAC/LO/D82
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FORMAT SPECIFICATION FOR LUND SIMULATED DATA INPUT TO DELFT RGC SOLUTION
(PROPOSAL)

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1. Tape format

Magnetic tape, 1600 BPI, 9 tracks, phase encoded.

No label.

80 ASCII characters per logical record (no LF, CR), padded with blanks when necessary.

A physical record (block) contains an integer number of logical records. The maximum blocklength is 28800 characters = 360 logical records. Normally the maximum blocklength is used except for the last block in the file, which may be shorter (no blank records are inserted to reach a fixed blocklength).

The first block of the first file is not preceded by any label or EOF mark. The files are separated by a single EOF mark. Two EOF marks follow the last file on the tape. There is no information about the actual number of blocks and logical records in a file other than the EOF mark.

A tape contains not more than ONE simulation run. This is identified by a CHARACTER*8 variable called `tapeid`. `tapeid = 'LOSIM3 '` for the next simulation to be produced in Lund.

2. Files

For one simulation run (normally 5 consecutive spins = one RGC) the tape will contain three files, viz.:

- File #1: 'MCL' (Mission control local) - general data about the RGC, eclipses, and gas jets
- File #2: 'FIS' (Fixed information on stars) - gives the assumed and true geometric positions of the stars in the RGC system, photometric data, etc
- File #3: 'FRAME' (Frame data) - gives all data needed on a frame-by-frame basis: attitude (assumed and true), number of objects observed in the frame, and data for each observation (grid phase, correction to apparent

position, etc)

The approximate sizes are 0.005, 0.5, and 10 Mb, respectively. The detailed content and format of each file is specified below.

2.1. MCL - Mission control local

record#	content	format
1	'MCL ',tapeid	A5,X,A8,66X
2	IDRGC,ECLON,ECLA,TIMBEG,TIMEND	I6,2F16.12,2F15.8,12X
3	NECLIP,NBGJET	2I6,68X
4	ECLIP1(I),I=1,4	4F15.8,20X
5	ECLIP2(I),I=1,4	4F15.8,20X
6	NUMFRA(1),TIME(1)	I6,F13.6,61X
.	.	.
.	.	.
5+NBGJET	NUMFRA(NBGJET),TIME(NBGJET)	I6,F13.6,61X

Comments:

- IDRGC = integer (1 to 3000) identifying the RGC
- ECLON,ECLA = ecliptical longitude, latitude of RGC pole [rad]
- TIMBEG,TIMEND = MJD for beginning of first, last frame
- NECLIP = number of eclipses (0 to 2)
- ECLIP1(1:4) = timing information for first eclipse [decimal frame#]
- ECLIP2(1:4) = timing information for second eclipse [decimal frame#]
- NBGJET = number of gas jets
- NUMFRA(1:NBGJET) = integer frame# for each gas jet = INT(TIME(.))
- TIME(1:NBGJET) = decimal frame# for each gas jet

2.2. FIS - Fixed information on stars

record#	content	format
1	'FIS ',tapeid	A5,X,A8,66X
2	IDRGC,NOBJ	2I6,68X
3*k	IDOBJ,IDHIP,HMG,BMV,RMSHMG,RMSBMV, IFP,IFS,IFC,IFV,IFM	2I7,4F7.3,5I4,18X
3*k+1	TMEAN,PSIB,QSIB,RMSPSI,RMSQSI	F15.8,4F16.2,X
3*k+2	PSIT,QSIT	15X,4F16.12,X
(k = 1 to NOBJ)		

Comments:

- IDRGC = see 2.1
- NOBJ = number of objects (stars)
- IDOBJ = object identification within the RGC (21 to 20+NOBJ)
- IDHIP = Hipparcos object identification (1 to 120000 approx)
- HMG = magnitude H
- BMV = colour index B-V
- RMSHMG,RMSBMV = standard errors for HMG, BMV
- IFP = 1 for primary star, 0 otherwise [1]
- IFS = 1 for photometric standard, 0 otherwise [1]

IFC = 1 for constant star, 0 otherwise [1]
 IFV = 1 for veiling glare star, 0 otherwise [0]
 IFM = 1 for single star, 2 for double [1]
 (In LOSIM3, these flags will always have the values given in brackets.)
 TMEAN = mean time of observation in MJD
 PSIB, QSIB = best available estimates of the geometric position at
 time TMEAN (abscissa, ordinate in rad)
 RMSPSI, RMSQSI = standard errors of PSIB, QSIB in rad
 PSIT, QSIT = true geometric position (abscissa, ordinate in rad)

2.3. FRAME - Frame data

record#	content	format
1	'FRAME', tapeid	A5,X;A8,66X
2	IDRGC;NFR	2I6,68X
+1	IDFR;NOBJ;NSTAR;NPLAN;TIME	4I6;F13.6,43X
+2	PSI;TET;PHI;PSID;RMSPSI	5F16.12
+3	PSIT;TETT;PHIT	3F16.12,32X
+3+k	IDOBJ;IDFOV;DPSI;DQSI;G;H;NGRID; IPHGRD;IPHRMS	I4,I3,2F16.12,2F10.6,3I7

(k = 1 to NOBJ)
 (There are NFR groups of 3+NOBJ records following the first two records.)

Comment:

IDRGC = see 2.1
 NFR = number of frames (the three records +1, +2, +3 are given
 also for empty frames, e.g. during occultations)
 IDFR = frame# (0 to NFR-1)
 NOBJ = number of objects observed in the frame (0 to 10)
 NSTAR = number of stars observed in the frame (0 to 10)
 NPLAN = number of planets observed in the frame (0 to 10)
 (NOBJ = NSTAR + NPLAN)
 TIME = frame mid-time [decimal frame#] = IDFR + 0.5
 PSIE, TETE, PHIE = Euler 3-2-1 angles for the assumed attitude w.r.t. RGC
 at time TIME, in radians
 PSID = assumed time derivative of PSIE [rad/T4]
 RMSPSI = standard error for PSIE [rad]
 PSIT, TETT, PHIT = true attitude angles [rad]
 IDOBJ = object identification within the RGC (1 to 3000)
 IDFOV = FOV identifier, -1 for following, +1 for preceding
 DPSI, DQSI = corrections 'apparent minus geometric' in abscissa
 and ordinate [rad]
 G, H = (approximate) field coordinates in [rad]
 (origin at grid centre; images move along +G; +H towards QSI > 0)
 NGRID = slit number = NINT(G/1.208")
 IPHGRD = modulation phase at frame mid-time, expressed as an
 integer multiple of 1e-5 radians (0 to 628319)
 IPHRMS = standard error for IPHGRD in units of 1e-5 rad